

ISic1134

I.Sicily inscription 1134

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object

statue base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 3

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [ΠόπλιοςΚορνή]λιος Ποπλίου υἱὸς
2. [ΣκιπίωνἈφρικαν]ὸς ὕπατος (vac.undefined) ἐλῶν
3. [Καρχηδόνακατά] κράτος τοὺς (vac.undefined) ἐξ
4. [Ἰμέρας ἀνδριάν]τ,ας Ἰμέραῖοις []

Apparatus

Text of IGTermini

Translation (en)

Poplios Kornelios Skipion Afrikanos, son of Poplios, consul, after having taken Carthage by storm, (restored) the statues (taken) from Himera to the Himeraioi

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284794

EDCS 64900560

EDCS 65000038

Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 201-202

Degrassi, A. 1965. *Inscriptiones Latinae Liberae Rei Publicae*. Florence. At 326

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1134. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351593>

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